

THE EVOLUTION OF THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE UNIVERSE OVER COSMIC TIME

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All chemical elements heavier than O produced in supernova explosions.

Different supernova types (Ia, CC) but also different properties of the progenitor (initial mass, metallicity) and explosion mechanism influence the relative proportions of heavy metals produced.

Cas A
(SN core collapse)

expect to explode 10s of Myr after starburst

Kepler
(SN type Ia)

expect longer delay times than SNcc

The chemical evolution of the Universe as a whole reflects the explosion physics and **integrated star formation history** over cosmic time

Some heavy elements are incorporated into younger stars, but most metals are expelled from the host galaxies and reside in the IGM.

The metal distribution is an important tracer of stellar and AGN feedback and ram pressure stripping

What is the history of production of metals in the Universe?
(supernova physics and star formation)

What is the history of release of metals into the intergalactic
medium?
(physics of feedback, ram pressure stripping, mixing)

(How) DOES THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE UNIVERSE EVOLVE?

Galaxy metallicities

Erb et al. 2006

Older galaxies less metal-rich;
Older stars typically have a smaller
fraction of Fe-group to alpha-elements

But most metals in IGM not in stars!

Milky Way stars

From Kobayashi et al. 2006

THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION IN CLUSTER CORES

The peak in cool core clusters is probably due to metal production in the BCG. There is little new star formation here, so no SNcc (only stellar winds and SNIa contribute).

DO WE SEE AN EVOLUTION IN
SNIA TO SNCC PRODUCTS,
WITH SNIA MORE
PREDOMINANT IN THE MORE
ENRICHED GAS?

THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE ICM ON LARGE SCALES

Tamura et al. 2001, Boehringer et al. 2001,
Werner et al. 2006, Finoguenov et al. 2002,
Matsushita et al. 2003, Rasmussen & Ponman
2009, Lovisari et al. 2011

Gastaldello & Molendi 2002, de Plaa et al.
2006, Matsushita et al. 2007, Sato et al. 2009,
Lovisari et al. 2011, Bulbul et al. 2012,
Mernier et al. 2015

Initially it was thought that SNcc products are produced early and distributed uniformly throughout the ICM (by galactic winds!) but SNIa have a longer delay time and are added later, following the current stellar light distribution

THE CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF THE INTERGALACTIC MEDIUM: CHEERS PROJECT

Suzaku XIS reveals nearly constant chemical composition of the ICM in other galaxy groups out to larger radii

ASCA: Si/Fe ~2.3

VIRGO: THE NEAREST AND SECOND BRIGHTEST GALAXY CLUSTER

Over 1Ms observing time with Suzaku!
Probed chemical enrichment over such large spatial scales for the first time.

Simionescu et al. 2015

$[\text{Si}/\text{Fe}], [\text{S}/\text{Fe}], [\text{Mg}/\text{Fe}] \sim \text{solar}$
over a scale of 10 million ly

Fe/H shows strong gradient in the vicinity of the BCG, but X/Fe surprisingly consistent with solar throughout the entire volume of clusters!

Easiest explanation: SNcc and the bulk of SNIa explosions occur on similar time-scales after a starburst

Maoz et al. 2012, time delay distribution of SNIa using SDSS data (red points)

We know the peak of SNcc metal production was around $z \sim 2-3$
 A large fraction of SNIa must also have exploded by this time.
 Most of the metals in the IGM were already in place by $z \sim 2$!

WERE FE-GROUP ELEMENTS (PREDOMINANTLY FROM SNIa)
RELEASED INTO THE ICM EARLY (ON SIMILAR TIME SCALES AS SNCC)?
1: (Further) evidence from Low-redshift Clusters

If Fe were recently produced by the galaxies, M_{Fe} to K-band luminosity should be constant!

Entropy stratification makes it hard to mix Fe out to large radii at present times.

UNIFORM METALLICITY DISTRIBUTION IN THE PERSEUS CLUSTER

^{56}Fe abundance measurements across the cluster at different radii and azimuths show strikingly uniform distribution

METALLICITY FROM A SAMPLE OF CLUSTERS MAPPED BY SUZAKU

all robust abundance measurements beyond $0.25r_{200}$

- require signal to background $> 10\%$ around Fe-K
- minimal contamination by stray light and susceptibility to sky background systematics

WERE FE-GROUP ELEMENTS (PREDOMINANTLY FROM SNIa)
RELEASED INTO THE ICM EARLY?
#2: Evidence from High-redshift Clusters

WARPJ1415.1+3612 at $z = 1.03$
Metal peak already in place!
(de Grandi et al. 2014)

METALLICITY (NON-) EVOLUTION IN THE ICM OUT TO $z \sim 1$

Sample of 245 RASS and SPT clusters observed with Chandra, $0.5-1.0R_{500}$

$$Z = Z_0 \left(\frac{1+z}{1+z_{\text{piv}}} \right)^{\beta_{1+z}} \left(\frac{kT}{kT_{\text{piv}}} \right)^{\beta_{kT}}$$

Chandra only:
 $\beta_{1+z} = -0.30 \pm 0.91$

Chandra+Suzaku:
 $\beta_{1+z} = -0.35^{+1.18}_{-0.36}$
 $\sigma_{\ln z} = 0.00^{+0.07}_{-0.00}$

XLSSC 122

Mantz et al. 2017

$z \sim 2, Z \sim 0.33 \pm 0.18$

CHEMICAL ENRICHMENT HISTORY: WHAT TO LOOK FORWARD TO

AstroSAT: map metals in other nearby low-temperature clusters/groups of galaxies on large scales

Can we use Chandra and XMM-Newton to further prove the lack of evolution of the ICM metallicity with redshift?

+of course future high resolution spectroscopy with XARM/ATHENA!